

THE MICRO-OPTICS REVOLUTION IN AUTOMOTIVE LIGHTING

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ABSTRACT

Wafer-level micro-optics is a key component for many optical modules or systems. Refractive and diffractive micro-optical components are used for fiber coupling (tele-/datacom), laser- and light shaping for light sources from DUV to far IR, in medical devices, sensors, metrology, and consumer products (smart phones). Micro-optics has played and is still playing a major role in photolithography (wafer steppers), bringing down resolution from 1 micron to some nanometers feature size. More recently, microlens arrays (MLA) have been introduced to automotive lighting. Reducing weight, packaging size and power consumption are key for the future of cars, especially electric vehicles (EV).

KEYWORDS: Micro-optics, microlens, microlens array, wafer-level-optics, automotive lighting, head lights, light carpets

INTRODUCTION

Micro-optics manufacturing technology had been developed at universities in the 1980s and was transferred to industry in the late 1990s. The basic idea behind is the parallel manufacturing of many miniaturized “planar” optical components on larger substrates or wafers, as shown in the following chapter.

WAFER-LEVEL MANUFACTURING OF MICROLENS ARRAYS (MLA)

Microlens arrays (MLA) are typically manufactured by wafer-level technology like (a) reflow and reactive ion-etching (RIE) and (b) by imprint lithography as shown in Figure 1 and Figure 3.

Figure 1: Wafer-level-manufacturing of microlens arrays (MLA) by photolithography, reflow and reactive ion-etching (RIE). This technology allows to manufacture spherical and aspherical microlens arrays for the highest quality requirements in Fused Silica (SiO_2) and Silicon (Si).

Wafer-level manufacturing also allows to place additional features like trenches, pupils, pinholes, alignment marks, etc. on both sides of the wafer, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Wafer-level-manufacturing allows to place different microlens arrays, diffractive optical elements, and additional features on both sides of the wafer with very high precision.

For consumer applications and automotive lighting, micro-optics is typically manufactured by imprint lithography as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Wafer-level-manufacturing of microlens arrays (MLA) by imprint lithography. This technology allows to manufacture spherical and aspherical microlens arrays, pupils, wafer stacks and complete optical systems at large volume for very competitive manufacturing costs.

MICROLENS ARRAYS (MLA) FOR AUTOMOTIVE LIGHTING

In 2014 the Fraunhofer IOF in Jena presented a first microlens-based “light carpet” for decorative applications in automotive lighting. The fly’s-eye configuration allows projection of sharp pattern on tilted or even curved surfaces with uniform intensity. Welcome light carpets have become standard for premium cars in the meantime. Applications for safety (blinker, warning) are in development and might be standard in car industry within the next five years.

Figure 4: Light carpets (a) welcome light carpet for BMW series 3, (b) light carpet for safety

More recently micro-optics is also used for head lights. First cars with microlens-based head lights are delivered to customers now.

Figure 5: Microlens Array (MLA) headlights, (a) Lucid Air, (b) Genesis G90

Microlens arrays (MLA) allow to shrink the head light of a car significantly, which is a major advantage regarding space, weight, and energy consumption especially for electric vehicles. MLA head lights could have any form or shape allowing full design freedom, like the recent trend to slim or ultra-slim head lights. Light is visible innovation for car industry and the new MLA technology is one of the most promising technology approaches today.

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